

IMPORTANCE OF LAND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN OUR COUNTRY TODAY

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Abstract.

Management of land relations - covers all social relations. Relationships include social, economic, legal, environmental and other types of governance.

Key words.

economic, legal, ecological, object, subject, subject,

In the process of changing the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, effective forms of management of land relations and land resources are manifested. In addition to its main characteristics, the land has become a means of production of this resource, a regional business, a natural resource, territorial relations and an object of real estate.

Therefore, new principles and methods are needed to create an effective system of land resources management, regional and local self-government, attracting investments, providing guaranteed rights to subjects of land relations, which will allow increasing taxation and budget revenue collection. will come.

In the conditions of market relations, the development of land leasing as the most effective and economically expedient form of land use, which ensures the increase of budget revenues, is especially important. At the same time, it will be of decisive importance to mediate a uniform procedure in the state management of land relations, to produce a reasonable method of rent, to take into account the state of the regional economy that clearly reflects the state of the land market, and to take into account the priority of forming a set of measures in the land rent policy in the management system of the process in it. . It is necessary to develop a methodological theory of regulating land relations, to activate the forms and

methods of land sales, to encourage the processes of privatization of land plots, investment, evaluation, insurance activities, mortgage lending, transactions with valuable land securities.

Management of land relations - covers all social relations. Relationships include social, economic, legal, environmental and other types of governance. Currently, debates between the public of Uzbekistan and economic scientists about the mechanism of development of land relations have expanded:

In our opinion, the management of land relations is a systematic and purposeful influence of the state and society on the management of land resources. This influence encourages to know the objective laws and to apply them in life in order to ensure the effective use of the country's land resources. Land resources management should include: control over land use, organization, regulation, planning.

The basis of the land resources management system is the object, subject, subject, goal, tasks and management function. It is necessary to know the object and subject of management with the result of historical social processes. Subject and object types of management are inextricably linked. For example, it is very different from the management of land plots of high-rise buildings.

The purpose, essence and function of land resource management determine the social, economic and political movement of the independent society of Uzbekistan today.

The object of management is the land fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its subjects are administrative-territorial units, administrative districts, cities, certain land properties of land ownership, land use in legal status, which differs in the description of land use, and also does not include land use (general use lands) are plots of land.

The subject of management is the process of organizing land use, which provides for the diverse needs of the population within a certain territorial boundary. The needs dictate the application of various methods of land use management.

Such methods include:

- Territorial organization within the boundaries of land users;
- Engineering support of the land use process (engineering communications);
- Studying the legal status of the land plot (ownership, purpose of use, rent, demarcation, maintenance duties, etc.);
- Establishing the types of land use (allowed use) and directions;

- Implementation of effective economic and ecological technologies in land use;
- Analysis of the natural and economic condition of the land;
- Other activities that affect the quantity and quality of the land and its status.

Today, the main tasks of the control over the use of land and their protection are to ensure compliance with the requirements of legal documents of legal entities and individuals, state management bodies, and local government bodies.

State control over the use of lands and their protection is carried out by local state authorities, as well as state bodies with special powers.

Nature protection societies, scientific societies and other public associations, as well as citizens, are assisted by state bodies and self-governing bodies of citizens of settlements, villages and villages in the implementation of control over the use of land and their protection.

Local administration is carried out by local self-government bodies. Management may also have a special recommendation in this regard. Land management is carried out by land plot users and property owners themselves.

The management of land resources has a complex description, because it concerns the interests of the subjects of land relations, therefore, it creates the need to apply a systematic approach to the management of the process of use and protection of land resources. It requires linking organizational and technological solutions with possibilities of ecological and economic consequences. Land resources management is carried out by the legislative and executive bodies of the government. They tax land relations and determine overall strategy for land ownership, land conservation activities, and so on.

The content of the activity of the executive bodies for the management of land resources consists in planning and forecasting the use of land resources.

According to the function of information in the management process, it is divided into the following:

- to inform (used to justify the decision made);
- the management process is formed and delivered to the entity for execution and use;
- collection of information, processing and its analysis determines the essence of the integrated management system. Therefore, it is important to determine the components of information management and their interrelationship at administrative territorial levels.

The source of information can be the materials of the land cadastre and other agencies, as well as executive bodies of the government: cartographic material, registers, reports, books and records, catalogs, abstracts, expert information, dictionaries and other inspection and analysis materials.

The assessment of the dynamics of the current situation of land resources management is carried out as follows.

1. Assessing the existing law of the political-economic situation in the district (city) government, region, region and country and determining the main goals in the field of land resources management and determining the reasons that prevent them from being achieved;

It is planned to establish a plan of activities to achieve the goal.

Regional and district (city) authorities should implement land resource management based on the following situation:

2. land plots belong to the population living in specific areas and to the state. Therefore, it is necessary to coordinate between district (city), regional and state bodies of the executive power on issues of responsibility for issuing orders on their use and use of land resources;

3.all residents of the region should benefit from the use of land resources;

According to the land code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, land use must be paid based on a lease agreement. The amount of payment for the use of land should be determined based on the results of the state land cadastral evaluation in accordance with the decisions of the regional government to the government bodies involved in land acquisition;

Land transactions (that is, all types of agreements related to land plots) must be carried out according to the rules established by the regional government. In this case, issuing an order on the distribution of land resources and their use should take into account the obligation to take into account the characteristics of the regional conditions stipulated in the agreement on the limitation of powers in the field of use;

If in the process of use it causes damage to the environment or the living conditions of the population, the governor of the region can influence any owners to limit their use of the land;

The executive bodies of the government, which carry out a number of tasks in relation to the general state management of land resources in relation to the entire land fund of the country.

In conclusion, it should be said that the interests of local self-government bodies and regional bodies in the field of land resources management are mostly

compatible. However, the interest of local self-governing bodies in the formation of the local budget takes into account the problem of land resource management, mostly only from a financial point of view..

The Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan also envisages the development and implementation of measures for the protection of the environment, including land resources, and the rational use of land resources. Such measures include rational organization of the territory, increase of soil fertility, protection of land from water and wind erosion, floods, flooding, corrosion, re-salination, erosion, production waste, contamination with chemical radioactive substances, conversion of damaged land into replanting fields. includes the like. Solving these issues should be based on complete and comprehensive information about the quality of the country's land resources. In particular, implementation of the laws "On Land Tax", "On Farming", "On Farming", implementation of agrarian reforms in agriculture development relies primarily on land cadastre data, and this in turn creates an understanding of the need to focus on the training of personnel who manage land and water resources wisely.

REFERENCES:

1. Imomov, S., Nuriddinov, K., & Nuriddinov, O. (2021). Thermal regime for convective drying products. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 264, p. 04055). EDP Sciences.
2. Xurramovich, N. O. (2021). Modern Improved Geodesical, Geoformatical and Cartographic Methods in Creation of the Atlas of Cultural Heritage Monuments in Bukhara Region. *Barqarorlik va Yetakchi Tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 1(1), 43-47.
3. Xurramovich, N. O. (2021). Reconstruction of Damaged Land in Farmers and Agricultural Farms. *Barqarorlik va Yetakchi Tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 1(1), 48-53.
4. Nuriddinov, O. X. (2022). Increasing the biological activity of salinated soils of Bukhara region with the help of various fertilizers. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 172-177.
5. Xurramovich, N. O., & Bekmurodovna, H. Z. (2022). The Main Problems of Ensuring the Implementation of the Uniform State Policy Directed to the Wise Use of Earth Resources and Their Protection. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 14, 31-34.

6. Khurramovich, N. O. (2022). Determination and Assessment of Places at Risk of Desertification Using Geoinformation Technologies. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 15, 56-58.
7. Xurramovich, N. O., & Bekmurodovna, H. Z. (2022). The Place and Role of Ecology in Geographic Information Systems. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 14, 51-54.
8. Xurramovich, N. O., Bekmurodovna, H. Z., & Qizi, O. Z. A. (2022). Increasing the Biological Activity of Salinated Soils of Bukhara Region With the Help of Various Fertilizers. *Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*, 10, 23-26.
9. Nuriddinov, O. X., Jurayev, K. H. O. G. L., & Qo, X. Z. O. G. L. (2022). Increasing the biological activity of salinated soils of Bukhara region with the help of various fertilizers. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 172-177.
10. Khurramovich, N. O., Mukhayo, O., & Saidjonovich, H. F. (2023). USE OF RESOURCE-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES AND STUDY OF MINERAL FERTILIZER CONSUMPTION IN THE BUKHARA OASIS INCREASING THE PRODUCTIVITY OF IRRIGATED SOILS. *PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS*, 2(20), 84-91.
11. Atojevich, H. S., Xurramovich, N. O., & Tolibovna, A. N. (2023). PROCEDURE FOR STATE REGISTRY OF RIGHTS TO BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTIONS. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(4), 1137-1141.
12. Xurramovich, N. O., Hafiz o'g'li, J. K., & Fazliddin o'g'li, X. F. (2022). BUXORO VOHASI TUPROQLARINING MORFOLOGIK BELGILARI VA MEXANIK TARKIBI. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(13), 86-95.
13. Nuriddinov, X. U. R. R. A. M., & Nuriddinov, O. X. (2020). SRAVNITEL'NYE Kharakteristiki "GORYaChIX YaЩIKOV" ISPOLZUEMYX DLYa KOMBINIROVANNOGO GELIOSUSHILOK. In *Effektivnost primeneniya innovatsionnykh texnologiy i texniki v selskom i vodnom xozyaystve* (pp. 133-134).
14. Nuriddinov, X., Normamatov, Ch. K., Ruzikulov, J. U., & Nuriddinov, O. X. (2020). RASChET NAGREVATELYa KOMBINIROVANNYOY GELIOTEPLOVOY SUSHILKI. *Nauka i mir*, 1(4), 40-42.
15. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Yer Kodeksi. O'zbekiston Respublikasining yangi qonuni. 19-jild. T: Adolat, 1998
16. O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonuni - "Davlat Yer Kadastrı to'g'risi" da.

17. Bobojonov A.R. Raxmonov K.R. G'ofurov A.J. Yer kadastr. T: Cho'lpon, 2002

18. Bobojonov A.R. Ro'ziboyev S.B. Abdurahmonova I.Q. Yerdan Foydalanish asoslari (o'quv qo'llanma) T: TIMI, 2006